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The Book of abstracts contains the materials of invited, plenary and poster presentations reports on XXI International Conference on Inorganic Chemistry Ukraine (XXI ICICU) which take place in Uzhhorod June 3-6, 2024. At the conference were considered issues of solid state chemistry, solid inorganic materials, crystal chemistry, synthesis of new compounds for modern medicine and pharmaceutical chemistry, chemistry and physics of materials, atomic and electronic structure of solid inorganic materials, materials for "green" chemistry. The conference will cover issues on solid state chemistry, solid-state inorganic materials, crystal chemistry, synthesis of new compounds for modern medicine and pharmaceutical chemistry, materials chemistry and physics, atomic and electronic structure of solid inorganic materials, materials for "green" chemistry, etc. The reports contain the latest scientific results and advanced research methods in the field: 1. Chemistry of inorganic and coordination compounds, including medicinal and pharmaceutical chemistry; 2. Characterization and properties of new inorganic substances, crystal chemistry; 3. Physical inorganic chemistry, nanochemistry; 4. Dual-use materials, alternative energy sources, environmental chemistry.

SYNTHESIS OF WEAKLY AGGLOMERATED FERROMAGNETIC NANOPARTICLES FOR MAGNETICALLY CONTROLLED ELEMENTS

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The search for methods to synthesize weakly agglomerated ferromagnetic nanoparticles is of immense scientific and practical significance. These materials hold promise for applications in various fields, such as magnetic recording systems and microwave systems. The properties of these systems can be adjusted using external magnetic fields. Weakly agglomerated nanoparticles are valuable in medicine, where they enhance contrast in MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging), act as carriers for targeted drug delivery, and can generate heat to destroy tumors in hyperthermia. Synthesizing nanoparticles is complex due to the dependence on various factors like synthesis method, chemical composition, crystal structure, and physical/chemical properties. Developing functional elements controllable by magnetic field for diverse applications using these weakly agglomerated nanoparticles presents an equally significant challenge.

The purpose of this study was to search for methods to synthesize weakly agglomerated ferromagnetic nanoparticles with spinel, perovskite, and barium hexaferrite structures, as well as to develop magnetically controlled elements for various applications.

Various methods (precipitation from solutions, reverse emulsions, sol-gel) were used for synthesizing nanoparticles. During the synthesis of barium hexaferrite nanoparticles using aqueous solutions, an initial amorphous precipitate formed, but subsequent heat treatment resulted in significant nanoparticle agglomeration, rendering them unusable. During deposition, the nanoparticles formed an ordered, fractal structure, which could be changed by altering the synthesis conditions. Our research identified specific conditions that led to a 3-level arrangement of nanoparticles within the amorphous precipitates. Heating these precipitates yielded weakly agglomerated crystalline nanoparticles with superior magnetic properties. Additionally, the feasibility of synthesizing barium hexaferrite nanoparticles with an anisotropic shape, which holds significant potential for magnetic recording systems, has been demonstrated. The degree of nanoparticle agglomeration was found to be affected by both the chemical composition and crystal structure of the material. Crystalline, weakly agglomerated nanoparticles with a spinel structure were successfully synthesized using aqueous and non-aqueous solutions without additional heating. This contrasts with barium hexaferrite and perovskite nanoparticles, which require heat treatment due to their higher crystalline formation energy. The difference arises because the simpler structure of spinel makes its formation significantly easier and requires one order of magnitude less energy compared to barium hexaferrite and perovskite.

Using the synthesized weakly agglomerated nanoparticles, the magnetically controlled devices were developed, namely microwave element operating in the H01 δ mode, which operating frequency can be tuned. This tuning is achieved through a composite magnetic film made of a polymer filled with weakly agglomerated magnetic nanoparticles. The proposed approach offers simple film preparation and applicability to complex shapes and large areas, making it promising for various resonant microwave structures. The possibility of creating left-handed metamaterials, which exhibit a negative value of both magnetic permeability and electrical permittivity, was shown. The ability to control these properties allows the development of novel microwave devices with functionalities not achievable with traditional materials. Multilayer systems based on ferromagnetic and ferroelectric phases were developed, with magnetic properties influenced by an electric field.

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